

IMPLEMENTED REFORMS ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM INFRASTRUCTURE

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Annotation. This article provides information on investments, stages of tourism development and measures aimed at the tourism sector.

Keywords: Project, investment, infrastructure, capacity, tour operator, socio-psychological, network, visa, traditional, currency, market.

The ultimate goal of the large-scale reforms implemented in all areas today is to further develop the economy of our country and improve the well-being of our people. Tourism is one of the important sectors of the economy. With the effective use of existing opportunities, it is necessary to further improve this network, which is required by the times itself, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev.

Uzbekistan is a convenient country for both travel and pilgrimage. Because our ancestors, who are known and famous all over the world, settled down forever in our motherland. There is great interest in the rich spiritual and cultural heritage left by them in the international arena. For the further development of the industry, first, the improvement of the necessary infrastructure.

New prospects for tourism are opening up in our country, and comprehensive projects are being implemented in various directions. In particular, in recent years, new tourist destinations such as mountaineering, horse, camel, bicycle travel, off-road travel, fishing, ecotourism, educational tourism, medical tourism have become popular.

The decree of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev dated December 2, 2016 "On measures to ensure the rapid development of the tourism sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan" ensures the rapid development of the tourism industry, gives tourism the status of a strategic sector of the economy, and the potential of tourism in the regions is an important factor in effective use.

Currently, in the development of international tourism in the countries of the world, great attention is paid to increasing the socio-economic importance of tourist enterprises. In order to ensure that a broad segment of the population will actively contribute to the tourism sector, which has become one of the four priority sectors in the world, that is, they will participate on a large scale in the organization of various tourist services, and as a result, they will increase the social and economic interests of the countries. The role of private tourist enterprises and organizations is significant.

Investment activity in a travel agency is one of the main directions in the initial development of planning. Investment decisions are directed to the development and implementation of investment projects, including production restructuring, technical rearmament, creation of new products (services) and reorganization of the organizational structure.

Based on the understanding of the basis of the investment project, tourism investment is explained in the following form. In order to meet a part of the current and future tourism demand, projects with the goal of offering tourism-related products and services to the economy, prepared and formulated in accordance with the economic principle, are called "Tourism Investment Project". We present the following explanation based on the tourism investment project, within the characteristics of the tourism sector. The tourism investment project aims to evaluate the existing tourism potential, meet the demand of local and foreign tourists, create new training opportunities, and help the national development by realizing foreign currency entry into the country, get profit in the

commercial area, produce and sell tourism products and services. is a sum of project works aimed at the construction and use of departments.

The impact of tourism demand on investment is also difficult to measure and evaluate, as it often depends on non-economic factors, even if it is studied within market tasks during the preparation stage of various investment projects. Demand for internal and external tourism is not only influenced by economic factors such as income, but also several factors such as fashion, exhibition, consumer atmosphere, snobbery, and socio-psychological factors are the influencers of tourism demand. A good study of the tourism market, the use of survey questionnaires, and continuous market monitoring are necessary. However, it is necessary to know that projects in the tourism sector are never ordered and captured in a simple form like any other sector project. For this reason, it is very difficult to discuss alternative investment projects among sectors. Since tourism investment projects have a high impact on the national economy, and their profits are much less satisfactory than in other sectors, alternative projects take the main place in the evaluation of these projects, and it is based on the appropriate use of incentive measures of the projects. For developing countries, there are incalculable benefits to integrated physical planning.

The state plays an important role in the development of tourism infrastructure under any conditions, especially during the transition to a market economy. Almost all countries try to increase the importance of the tourism industry in their national economy. Because tourism has the following priorities in the development of the national economy: a source of providing local workforce with qualified work and living conditions; market formation and capital investment flow mechanism; construction (hotels, campsites, motels), communication (cellular, and optical communication), transport (cars, buses, railway cars of international standards, airplanes), as well as service infrastructure (gas stations) means of introduction of new technologies and know-how in such

fields; means of development of national folk crafts; factors of stabilization of the political and socio-economic situation in the country and region; methods of preservation of historical monuments and cultural heritage; means of effectively increasing the foreign currency income of the state. In general, the state creates legal and economic foundations for the development of tourism infrastructure, prepares personnel for this sector, simplifies the visa system, and develops the production of tourist products and traditional goods.

After the independence of our country, the development of tourism became a priority issue with the direct initiatives of the President. In general, the development of tourism infrastructure in the Republic of Uzbekistan can be divided into five stages.

The first stage (includes 1992). This stage is characterized by the initial formation of national tourism in our republic. At this stage, the "Uzbektourism" National Company, considered the leader in tourism infrastructure, was founded.

The second stage (1993-1995 - years). A national development model of tourism was developed. This stage is associated with the development of new tourist destinations, improvement of service delivery, expansion of the material and technical base of tourism, improvement of the organizational system of management and other similar tasks, together with the increase in the volume of tourist services. Created a number of problems that could not be solved only within the framework of the national company "Uzbektourism". For the purpose of direct contact with tourist operators, the company has opened its doors in Germany (Frankfurt-Main), England (London), USA (New York), and United 1 Fayzieva Sh.R. Improving the economic mechanism of tourism development in Uzbekistan. Candidate thesis. UzMU opened its representative offices in countries such as the United Arab Emirates (Sharjah) and Russia (Moscow) in 2006.

The third stage (1995-1997 - years). The process of privatization in the field of tourist services has begun. At the beginning of 1996, about 90% of the total

amount of tourist objects in the system of the national company "Uzbektourism" was removed from the state.

The fourth stage (includes 1998). At this stage, an opportunity was created to increase the export potential, to ensure a stable flow of currency, tourists, and investments. The formation of national tourism at the level of world standards in the republic, the restructuring of the service infrastructure indirectly related to tourism, in particular, the border, customs and airport services that welcome tourists from abroad, have begun.

The fifth stage (periods after May 1999). At this stage, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the State Program for the Development of Tourism" not only formed a political basis for strengthening the position of national and international tourism in the country, but also gave an opportunity to strengthen its economic basis. Based on this regulatory document, additional tax benefits were granted to tourist enterprises. In addition, the position of tourism consultant was introduced in the diplomatic missions of Uzbekistan in foreign countries. In August of this year, the Parliament of the country adopted the Law "On Tourism", and as a result, the legal basis of the activity of the tourism sector was further improved.

Having chosen the path of transition to a market economy, our country is on the path of development by using the positive results achieved in the world experience as a model in the field of tourism, as in other fields. However, because we are one of the young countries that are just entering the market economy, we should bring the level of activity of private companies to a high level in all parts of the above classification. Because our government is creating all necessary conditions for the development of the tourism sector. In addition, the reforms implemented by our state in the field of tourism infrastructure development are yielding positive results.

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